

MEA vs CICES: Comparative Applicability for Assessing Ecosystem Services in B.R. Hills.

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SAGE Senior Ambassador: Mansi Singal

Supervisor: Dr. Manisha Sinha

Project: Valuation

Contributors: Deepanjana Saha, Dr. G. Ravikanth

Abstract

Ecosystem services are critical for human well-being, yet, categories such as regulating services remain largely unrecognised and undervalued due to the indirect nature of benefits. This study conducts a comparative review of two popular frameworks, Millennium Ecosystem Assessment and Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services, to evaluate their applicability to the socio-ecological context of B.R. Hills landscape. B.R. Hills is home to the Soliga tribal community and like any other mountainous ecosystem, is on the verge of decline. Frameworks were compared based on eight criteria including, ES definition and Classification, trans-disciplinarity, inclusion, community engagement, scalability, coherence and precision. Results show that MEA acknowledges the role of local knowledge in ecosystem management and links ES to human well-being, it therefore excels in inclusivity, resilience and community engagement criteria. Whereas, CICES is able to provide greater scalability and precision through its hierarchical classification system, through its structure, CICES is able to provide standardized accounting of two very important services namely water regulation and climate regulation. In B.R. Hills landscape, regulatory services support both ecological resilience and community livelihood, both the frameworks serve complementary strengths. A hybrid model that makes best use of MEA's participatory strength and CICES's technical rigor will be the most suitable for valuing and understanding the regulatory services. This hybrid model when combined with further field analysis will provide a foundation for developing context specific indicators and a stronger valuation framework.

Keywords: Regulatory ecosystem services, Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA), Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES), B.R. Hills.

Introduction

Ecosystem services (ES) are the direct and indirect contributions of ecosystems to human well-being. The world that is highly dependent on the resources from natural sources, often adopts strategies that are exploitative, and unstructured in nature, this leads to misuse of the Ecosystem Services. These exploitative strategies and lack of recognition of ecosystem services in economic decision making is what led to interest in identifying, valuing, measuring and mapping them (De Groot et al., 2012). Since then, the research in the field of ecosystem services has made a lot of progress over the past few decades in understanding the process that create ecosystem services, determining their value, mapping their supply and demand, and also analysing the dangers that ecosystem services face and their long-term effects (Fu et al., 2013). Among these, *regulating services* such as water regulation and carbon sequestration remain undervalued due to their intangible nature. This undervaluation is especially critical in ecologically fragile and socially complex mountain regions like B.R. Hills in India, where the local Soliga tribe depends heavily on these invisible benefits.

Mountainous ecosystems have distinctive topology, distinct climatic conditions, along with very diverse ecosystems which are very sensitive to the pressures put by human beings. These sensitive ecosystems provide a plethora of ecosystem services which are utilized by the local communities and contribute to their overall sustenance and quality of life (Rahmonov et al., 2021). B.R. Hills is one such landscape, where the Soliga tribe has a symbiotic relationship with nature, the sustenance of people of tribal community is based on shifting cultivation and collection of Non Timber Forest Produce (Madegowda & Rao, 2017)

B.R. Hills are situated on the boundary of the Western ghats, which provide several regulatory ecosystem services (Molur, 2011); the majority of which are now under threat, which makes regulatory ecosystem services assessment in such climate-sensitive regions even more important. Regulatory services have largely been unrecognized and undervalued due to the indirect nature of benefits; hence, they are overlooked in evaluation as well as decision-making processes (Mengist et al., 2020). B.R. Hills also provides these regulatory services in the form of water regulation, which acts as a watershed feeding into the Cauvery River system, and the region's forest also facilitates carbon sequestration by absorbing CO₂ and mitigating climate change (Akash et al., 2017). These ecosystem services are essential not just for the ecological health of the B. R. Hills landscape but also for the survival of the Soliga tribe, which is solely dependent on the services of the landscape for survival. The Soliga tribe back in 2011 had become India's first tribal population to reside inside the core zone of a tiger reserve and to this date they have protected their subsistence activities as well as their cultural practices (Balasubramanian & Sangha, 2021).

Millennium Ecosystem Assessment came in 2005 (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005) and Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services was first published in 2010 (Haines-Young, n.d.), these are among two most common frameworks still being used all over the world to untangle the mysteries of ecosystem services of various landscape. The goal of this review is to compare and contrast these two frameworks with regard to ecosystem

services and suggest ways for them to be adapted to the social ecological context of B.R. Hills.

Millennium Ecosystem Services Framework largely divides the services in four categories, namely, the Provisioning Services, Regulatory Services, Supporting Services and Cultural Services. It mentions a total of 24 Ecosystem services and identifies the trends in obtaining as well as the availability over the past five decades. (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005) The framework document also identifies the change in obtaining these services over the past few decades and provides a framework for the strength of linkages between the services and human well-being. (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005) The linkage is being depicted in the flowchart mentioned below:

Figure 1: Linkages between Ecosystem Services and Human Well-Being. Source: (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005)

Another framework that will form part of this review paper is The Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES). CICES, developed by the European Environment Agency (Haines-Young, n.d.), builds on the widely recognized MEA, 2005, but further provides a more detailed account of measuring the services that are directly involved in human well-being.

CICES classifies in three categories namely, Provisioning Services, Regulation and Maintenance Services, and Cultural Services. It provides a detailed account of each service and service type by sub-dividing them into 'Division', 'Groups', and 'Classes'. A more recent version of the framework allows its flexible application to different ecosystem types (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018)

CICES has also been designed to compare it to other popular frameworks such as TEEB, IBPES, and MEA. The Cascade model by Potschin and Haines-Young, 2016b, summarizes the essence in which CICES is set. The main goal of CICES is to conceptualize the end products of ecosystems that finally reach human beings and further understand the value that they add to life (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018).

Figure No. 2: The cascade model. Source: (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2016)

Methods

This review employs the systematic review methodology to compare and contrast the two widely popular frameworks, Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) and Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services framework (CICES).

The methodology is being employed in three stages:

1. A fundamental review of literature to understand the foundation and applicability of both the frameworks.
2. A detailed comparative analysis of both frameworks, based on the Both the frameworks were compared based on the five criteria developed by (Nahlik et al., 2012) and three additional criteria. The eight criteria used are:
 - Ecosystem Services (ES) definition and classification system.
 - Trans-disciplinarity.
 - Community Engagement.
 - Cohesiveness and Coherence.
 - Resilience.
 - Scalability.

- Inclusiveness.
- Precision.

3. Reporting the theoretical applicability of whole or specific parts of both the frameworks to the social-ecological context of B.R. Hills.

Information Sources and search strategy:

The search was conducted across three major academic databases, Google Scholar and Web of Science. This search was also supplemented by the relevant grey literature from the websites of European Environment Agency, United Nations Environment Programme and Millenium Ecosystem Assessment. Following keywords were used to carry out the search: “Ecosystem Services” AND “Valuation”, “MEA Framework” or “Millenium Ecosystem Assessment”, “CICES” or “Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services”, “Ecosystem Services” AND “Framework”. Only the studies published post 2005 were considered to include the publication and subsequent development of MEA and CICES Framework.

Eligibility Criteria:

Clear inclusion and exclusion criteria have been set for the literature, to ensure a targeted and relevant review. These inclusion criteria are focused on the results of the second stage, that is, comparing and contrasting both the frameworks.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Publication period must be from 2005 to 2025 since MEA findings were published in 2005(citation) and it will ensure the capturing of evolution of both the frameworks over time.
2. Studies that explicitly discuss or compare and contrast, MEA and CICES.
3. Studies that focus on ecosystem services classification and valuation based on a framework.
4. Studies that compare frameworks other than MEA and CICES.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Studies published before 2005 were excluded.
2. Studies that focus on Ecosystem Services Valuation based on independent methodology for each service.
3. Opinion pieces, or book reviews without original research or framework analysis.
4. Studies not accessible through open access or institutional subscriptions.

Results

The objective is not to choose a winner based on the criteria, rather to select components from both the frameworks that will be more relevant to the socio-ecological context of B.R. Hills. The comparative analysis is discussed in the following sections.

ES DEFINITION AND CLASSIFICATION SYSTEM:

MEA connects the ecosystem services to ‘human well-being’ and gives a straight forward definition of ecosystem of services as “benefits people obtain from the environment”. The services have been classified in four categories, namely, Provisioning, Supporting, Regulatory, and Cultural. The key goal of the assessment was to present a language that is understandable even by non-specialists (Carpenter et al., 2009). The classification has received criticism for mentioning “supporting services”, as it may pose risk of double counting (Fischer et al., 2022).

CICES does not explicitly define the Ecosystem Services, its goal was to provide a systematic process of accounting of ecosystem services and to address the classification challenge posed by MEA Classification. Its foundation, however, has been built on the MEA classification itself (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018). CICES has deliberately avoided classifying supporting services as a service category to prevent the double counting. It instead uses a five-level classification system, which moves from a broad level to a very specific one. It classifies services as:

Section → Division → Group → Class → Class type.

This nested and hierarchical structure makes this framework more suitable for studies related to mapping, valuation, and ecosystem accounting (Maes et al., 2016).

TRANSDISCIPLINARITY:

MEA is a radically transdisciplinary framework since the framing development involved experts from disciplines related to natural sciences, economics, social sciences, and inputs from the indigenous communities (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). The goal of this framework was to create an understanding around how ecosystems benefit and support human societies. The language and concepts were designed such that they are applicable and understandable across disciplines (Díaz et al., 2015).

CICES is viewed more as a technical tool rather than a transdisciplinary document. The tool has been developed primarily by environmental ecologists and economists, unlike MEA, which brought together experts from multiple disciplines (Haines-Young, n.d.). The main goal of CICES was to standardize the scientific classification, rather than to embed diverse worldviews from various disciplines (Müller & Burkhard, 2012). Therefore, MEA is inherently more transdisciplinary in design and theory.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT:

MEA links ecosystem services to human well-being and is more favourable to the component of community engagement. The approach of MEA is simple, direct and benefit focused, which makes it more applicable and accessible to the communities (Turnhout et al., 2013). The process of formulation of MEA in itself included case studies that focused on identifying the services relevant to communities and their well-being (Capistrano & Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (Program), 2005).

CICES is more technical and hierarchical in its nature and therefore, less befitting for community engagement, and the language is also more technical in nature which can be difficult to understand for non-experts (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018). CICES

becomes more suited for community engagement when either combined with other participatory frameworks or when the results are communicated to the community, but not in isolation (Kenter, 2016).

COHESIVE AND COHERENT:

The coherency of MEA has been criticized, particularly on the inclusion of supporting services as a separate category (Fisher et al., 2009), this lack of clear and stratified system of classification makes its application difficult for accounting purposes (Seppelt et al., 2011).

CICES was developed to increase the coherence in the classification system, and it has a strictly hierarchical nature which methodically separates the final products from the processes that produce them (Haines-Young, n.d.). It also has higher internal consistency making it a powerful tool for systematic accounting of ecosystem services across spatial and temporal scales (La Notte et al., 2017).

RESILIENCE:

MA conceptually considers resilience thinking by explicitly acknowledging the drivers, feedbacks, and thresholds that affect the supply of ecosystem services and human well-being (Carpenter et al., 2009; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). MEA's focus on socio-ecological dynamics and adaptive responses is closely aligned with other pivotal resilience studies (Folke, 2006), and its framing has been applied to assessments of vulnerability and resilience (Carpenter et al., 2009; Folke, 2006). Although CICES categorizes services and avoids confusing processes and benefits, it does not operationalize resilience in and of itself. However, when applied to dynamic assessment frameworks (such as the cascade model, SEEA EA, and scenario analyses), CICES can assist in monitoring changes in final service flows that indicate a loss of resilience (La Notte et al., 2017; Potschin & Haines-Young, 2016; *System of Environmental-Economic Accounting*, 2025).

PRECISION:

The MEA framework classifies ecosystem services into four categories. This classification provides conceptual clarity, but it lacks specificity while assessing regulatory sub-services, such as flood control, groundwater recharge, and drought mitigation. Because of this the MEA classification, becomes less reliable when accurate results are needed

(Carpenter et al., 2009; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). CICES, alternatively, provides a hierarchical classification which promotes the identification of specific regulatory services, such as breaking services down into a section, division, group, and class. The CICES framework is more accurate for valuation studies, with classifications clearly indicating global climate regulation (Class 2.2.6.1) and hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Class 2.2.1.3) (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018).

SCALIBILITY:

The MEA was intended to measure ecosystem services at a global level, but it has been adapted pretty universally at regional and local scales. However, the fact it does not have standardized categories endangers the ability to expect any comparability across sites and makes it impossible to aggregate the findings of various projects for national and

international policy (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). CICES, on the other hand, was explicitly designed to address issues associated with scalability at the level of nations and/or projects, while remaining aligned with assessments of ecosystem services in the EUs environmental accounting, and reporting obligations of the UN (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018). Its consistency allows data collected and assessed at the local scale to be easily aggregated into local- national and/or global policy.

INCLUSIVITY:

The MEA advocates inclusivity by clearly recognizing indigenous and local knowledge bodies along with their scientific counterparts, implying that sustainable management has to embrace a holistic approach (Díaz et al., 2015; Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). This advocacy is in accordance with diverse, community-dependent cultural landscapes like B.R. Hills, in which the Soliga community's ecological knowledge is central to forest management. CICES is relatively less inclusive. Its technical, value-free coding system claims not to represent values that are cultural, indigenous or community specific, which reduces its capacity to capture the diversity of worldviews of nature (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018)

Building on this comparative review, Table 1 summarizes the eight criteria selected for comparison of CICES and MEA frameworks.

S.No	Criteria	MEA	CICES
1.	Definition & classification	Broad, 4 categories (Provisioning, Regulating, Cultural, Supporting)	Hierarchical, 3 sections (Provisioning, Regulation & Maintenance, Cultural)
2.	Transdisciplinary	High, integrates ecology–economy–society	Low–medium, mainly ecology–economy
3.	Community engagement	Strong, local & indigenous knowledge	Weak, no direct community role
4.	Resilient	Focus on socio-ecological resilience, scenarios	Framework stability, not resilience focus
5.	Cohesive & coherent	Links ES to human well-being	Systematic coding, comparability
6.	Precision	Low Precision, Broad Categories. Limited for services like flood vs drought regulation	High precision, clear subclasses for water and climate regulation

7.	Scalability	Globally to locally adaptable but weak comparability across sites.	Highly scalable. Designed for international policies and reporting
8.	Inclusivity	Strong. Acknowledges knowledge systems and cultural values.	Limited. More technical and neutral in nature.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of MEA and CICES Across Eight Evaluation Criteria

Beyond the comparative analysis, specific components of CICES have been identified which will directly be relevant to valuation of regulatory services in B.R. Hills Socio-ecological context. Classes mentioned in Table 2 provide technical entry points, for regulatory services to be further mapped and measured. The indicators to map out these services are present in various other documents such as TEEB and IPBES.

CICES Class Code	CICES Class (Service)	Regulatory Service
2.2.1.3	Hydrological cycle and water flow regulation (Including flood control, drainage, natural irrigation, etc.)	Water regulation
2.2.6.1	Global climate regulation by reduction of greenhouse gas concentrations (e.g., by carbon sequestration)	Carbon sequestration / Global climate regulation
2.2.6.2	Micro- and regional climate regulation (e.g., vegetation effects on local temperature and humidity)	Local/regional climate regulation (co-benefit of carbon sequestration)

Table 2: Relevant CICES classes for regulatory Ecosystem Services. (Source: (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018))

MEA does not give an explicit classification into groups and classes, but mentions ways in which regulatory services have been valued in the past, the examples are embedded in the text, which have been summarised in Table 3.

MEA Category	Service (as written in MEA)	Examples of Valuation Methods Mentioned in MEA
Regulating Services	Water regulation	Examples include avoided damage costs (e.g., avoided flood damage), replacement

		cost (e.g., cost of building reservoirs or levees), and contingent valuation to capture willingness to pay for water flow regulation.
Regulating Services	Climate regulation (atmospheric composition & carbon sequestration)	Examples include carbon market valuation (price of carbon sequestration), social cost of carbon, and replacement cost approaches.

Table 3: Relevant MEA regulating services and associated valuation methods. Source: (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005)

DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis of MA, 2005 and CICES, 2009, demonstrates that these two are not conflicting frameworks, rather they are complementary to each other.

(Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005) was the first framework ever to classify ecosystem services at a larger scale. It provides a comprehensive and conceptual framework that focuses on using human well-being as a tool to demonstrate socio-ecological linkages. It also highlights the drivers of change in these socio-ecological systems. This framework is particularly helpful in understanding the complexity of ecosystems such as B.R. Hills, where the social, cultural, and provisional values are so deeply intertwined with the forest ecosystem (*Traditional Knowledge and Conservation | Economic and Political Weekly*, 2009) MEA advocates transdisciplinary research and also acknowledges the traditional ecological systems by again linking them to well-being (Carpenter et al., 2009; Díaz et al., 2015)

MEA framework proves to be effective particularly to map out the cultural embeddedness of ecosystem services, for Soliga community water is not merely a hydrological function but it also holds significant cultural and spiritual value, which are tied to sacred groves and traditional water use practices. These aspects resonate with MEA's focus on human well-being and resilience, however, MEA alone does not address the measurement and accounting issues related to valuation (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005)

CICES, on the other hand, provides a key element, standardized final-service classes that prevents double counting. It holds the advantage of breaking down these broad services into specific categories for measurement and reporting. For example, water regulation can be valued from the angle of flood protection, erosion control, and groundwater recharge. At the same time, carbon sequestration can be assessed using indicators of aboveground and belowground biomass (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018)

MEA's participatory framing, along with effective stakeholder engagement (Reed, 2008), helps choose important indicators. For example, (i) the baseflow maintenance index shows the days of perennial flow sustained in the late dry season, and (ii) the net ecosystem carbon balance is measured in tCO₂e per year by management unit. CICES offers clear codes for these final services, such as regulation of water flow and regulation of atmospheric composition through carbon sequestration and storage. This makes them compatible with hydrologic and carbon models, as well as accounting tables (Haines-Young & Potschin-Young, 2018; Maes et al., 2020). This approach addresses the traditional gap between concept and measurement highlighted by (Daily et al., 2009) and (Boyd & Banzhaf, 2007)

One significant finding after this comparative review is that neither MEA nor CICES, on its own, fully captures the ecological and cultural aspects of the services provided by BR Hills landscape. MEA is better at providing depth into the lives of Indigenous communities and helps us understand the value of intangible things, whereas, CICES provides more technical accuracy and policy relevance. And if we talk about the shortcomings, MEA although captures well-being in many dimensions, they lack granularity. On the other hand, classification systems like CICES provide precision but can oversimplify cultural and contextual realities. The case of B.R. Hills highlights these tensions and opens avenues for broader conversations in the field of ecosystem services sciences.

Conclusion and Future Directions

In the context of B.R. Hills, where forests regulate the water flows for drinking and agriculture and also sequester carbon, both frameworks are equally crucial. MEA captures them in a way that shows social realities and CICES makes sure that these services inform ecosystem accounts under the groups "regulation of baseline flows and extreme events" and "atmospheric composition and climate regulation" respectively. Table Number 2 introduced the classes which will be relevant to these particular regulatory services, the indicators to map out these services are present in various other documents such as TEEB and IPBES.

The classes provided in CICES serve as entry points for indicators of each service. Classes previously mentioned in this document are most suitable for the specific regulatory services of B.R. Hills. MEA does not give an explicit classification into groups and classes, but mentions ways in which regulatory services have been valued in the past, the examples are embedded in the text. In practical terms, both MEA and CICES serve as entry points for letting researchers develop their own indicators and must be used in a hybrid approach. This combined approach strengthens both scientific understanding and conservation efforts.

The current stage of research, however, has several shortcomings of its own. This review relies largely on the secondary literature data. More field visits are necessary to connect the comparative framework to real-life situations. Also, while MEA and CICES can be used for classification and basic understanding of Ecosystem Services, there is a need to work on an

indicator-based approach with respect to B.R. Hills. Indicator development will happen after several more months of literature review.

IPBES compiles the existing datasets in their documents “The methodological assessment report on SCENARIOS AND MODELS OF BIODIVERSITY AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES (2016)” and the “Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. (2019)”. Likewise, TEEB report mentions the indicators in illustrative examples. GIZ in their report titled “Indicators for Managing Ecosystem Services – Options & Examples” provides a comprehensive list of different services and scenarios which can prove to be helpful in indicator development.

Combining the inputs from all these frameworks can lead to a formulation of a contextually relevant and scientifically robust framework that is useful for long term ecosystem governance.

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